

How much of quorum sensing is microbial gasocrine signaling, and vice versa?

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Gasocrinology and planetary gasocrinology are emerging fields of study and areas of specializations, respectively (1, 2). The study of gasocrinology requires identifying all relevant gases, gasoreceptors and possibly riboceptors that sense these gases, as well as the feedback loops that maintain gas homeostasis (3–5). Because microorganisms play a significant role in these gasocrine processes and feedback loops, planetary gasocrinology requires expertise in microbial gasocrinology to understand how microbes interact with other organisms and abiotic sources involved in gasocrine processes.

Although microorganisms can communicate with other organisms via multiple mechanisms, some of the major microbiology education materials focus on quorum sensing molecules (or autoinducers) (6). However, quorum sensing, as a field, faces a similar challenge to that of gasotransmitters. Both fields are limited by how one defines a quorum sensing molecule or a gasotransmitter. For example, gases such as ethylene and dioxygen are excluded as gasotransmitters (7, 8). Likewise, while nitric oxide act analogously to quorum sensing molecules, nitric oxide is not yet widely recognized as a canonical quorum sensing molecule (9).

To advance planetary gasocrinology, it is necessary move beyond these narrow definitions. For example, dioxygen is a major gasocrine signaling molecule that is sensed via dioxygen gasoreceptors (e.g., *Escherichia coli* DosP phosphodiesterase and *Rhizobium meliloti* FixI kinase), protogasoreceptors such as hemoglobin orthologs with enzyme activity upon dioxygen unbinding, and possibly gas-sensing riboceptors (5, 10). At some point, we must ask: Can dioxygen be considered a quorum sensing molecule in a biofilm, with or without dioxygen-producing organisms? If so, does dioxygen also qualify as a quorum sensing molecule across an entire ecosystem or planet? Answering these questions will lead to a more challenging question: How much of quorum sensing is microbial gasocrine signaling, and vice versa?

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